

An Analysis of Speech Acts Used By The English Teacher In An Informal Context at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya

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ABSTRAK

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis jenis-jenis tindak tutur (speech acts) yang digunakan oleh guru bahasa Inggris dalam konteks informal di SMK Kesehatan Hamzar MT Pringgabaya. Tindak tutur merupakan aspek penting dalam interaksi antara guru dan siswa, terutama dalam menciptakan lingkungan belajar yang nyaman dan efektif. Pendekatan kualitatif digunakan dalam penelitian ini, dengan metode observasi dan perekaman sebagai instrumen utama. Pengumpulan data. Data dianalisis berdasarkan teori tindak tutur yang meliputi tindak lokusi, ilokusi, dan perlokusi, yang di gunakan oleh guru bahasa Inggris. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa guru lebih cenderung menggunakan jenis tindak tutur ilokusi seperti tindak direktif untuk memberikan instruksi, mengajak, memperingati, dan menyarankan. Penggunaan tindak tutur informal ini ternyata efektif dalam meningkatkan interaksi yang ramah antara guru dan siswa. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui jenis tindak tutur yang di gunakan oleh guru bahasa Inggris dalam konteks informal di SMK kesehatan Hamzar maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya..

ABSTRACT

The study aims to analyse the types of speech acts used by English Teacher in informal context at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya. Speech acts are an important aspect in the interaction between teachers and students, especially in creating a comfortable and effective learning environment. A qualitative descriptive approach was used in this study, with observation and recording methods as the main instruments of data collection. The data were analysed based on the theory of speech acts which include locution, illocution, and perlocution, used by English Teacher. The results showed that teacher were more likely to used illocutionary speech acts such as directive acts to instruct, invite, warn, and suggest. The use of informal speech acts is effective in increasing friendly interaction between Teacher and students. This study aims to determine the types of speech acts used by English Teacher in informal context at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya.

INTRODUCTION

English is recognized as one of the primary human languages with a crucial function in facilitating communication worldwide. Its status as an international language is evident in its widespread use across various aspects of life, particularly in the current global landscape characterized by intense competition. The language has evolved to be a key factor and measure of success in competitive environments. Hence, acquiring proficiency in English is paramount. It is noteworthy that English has spread and evolved, being embraced and adjusted as a universal mode of communication by diverse communities globally.

Language serves as a fundamental tool for interpersonal communication, enabling individuals to engage with others in various activities such as dialogue, verbal expression, and social interaction. As supported by Theodorson (1969), communication encompasses the exchange of information, ideas, attitudes, or emotions between individuals or groups. This process of communication involves conveying thoughts and messages through oral and written means. Effective communication relies on a shared understanding facilitated by a common language, ensuring clarity and comprehension between speakers and listeners.

Numerous factors contribute to the success of communication between speakers and listeners, or teachers and students. Particularly, the sensitivity exhibited by the speaker and listener in comprehending intentions and interpretations plays a vital role. Mere verbal expression is insufficient to ensure mutual

understanding, as misinterpretations can still arise. When a speaker communicates with a listener, their words not only convey a specific message but also reflect underlying intentions and desired actions. For instance, during an examination when a teacher announces 'time is up,' it could be a simple statement about the clock or a call to action for the listener. Understanding the speaker's true intent behind each utterance is crucial to effective communication and avoiding misunderstandings.

In the teaching-learning process, the teacher conveys information to students using effective language. However, there may be instances where students do not comprehend the message even though it is grammatically correct, resulting in miscommunication between teacher and student. Both teachers and students engage in producing verbal expressions during the teaching and learning activities, aiming to facilitate effective communication and achieve the learning objectives. These verbal interactions encompass both propositional and illocutionary meanings. Additionally, through these verbal exchanges, teachers aim to prompt students to engage actively in classroom activities."

Those phenomenon above described that Speech acts often occur in the learning process or in a formal context. However, It does not rule out the possibility that speech act also occur in an informal context or outside the learning process. This is reasonable because the actions of organizing certain activities, controlling students, and instructions are conducted through conversations between fellow teachers that contain speech acts. The utterances produced by teachers in an interaction with teachers or staff at school can create certain purposes and functions. In addition, some experts believe that the speech produced by teacher is a type of speech act, and speech acts theory has become a major part of linguistics. Therefore, speech acts are known as things that not only have an important role in the learning process but also outside of the classroom learning process or specifically, when involved in an interaction with fellow teachers or staff.

At the research location of the researcher SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya, Those phenomenon mentioned above also often occur in the process of teaching and learning English and used by the English teacher. The English teacher often performs speech acts in both contexts formal and informal contexts. Informal sounds are not very featuring speech acts by the English teacher at that research location but, It is still a possibility that the English teacher also performs speech acts in an informal context that is when the teacher conversation or interacts with fellow teachers or people that she interacts with, in SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya.

Example 1 :

Student: "Miss, may I be excused from the English class this afternoon? I have a student council activity."

Teacher: "Sure, that's fine. Don't forget to get a permission slip from the guidance counselor."

In this conversation, the illocutionary act occurs when the teacher gives permission to the student to skip the English class and instructs the student to get a permission slip from the guidance counselor. The teacher is not only conveying information but also giving clear permission and instructions to the student.

Example2 :

Student: "Miss, I saw you eating in the cafeteria earlier. What did you have?"

Teacher: "Oh, I had some fried snacks. They were really good!"

Student: "Oh, I like the cafeteria's fried snacks too. Thanks, Miss."

In this conversation, the locutionary act occurs through the student's question and the teacher's answer, which conveys simple information about what the teacher ate in the cafeteria. The Case above based on the observation and the occurrence that occur in SMK Kesehatan Hamzar MT Pringgabaya And the phenomenon above needs to be researched deeper So, The researcher is interested in discussing the speech acts of The English teacher in their interactions in an informal context. Then, The researcher has a purpose to study a problem related to the speech acts of the teacher with the title: "*An Analysis Of Speech Acts Used By The English Teacher In An Informal Context At Smk Kesehatan Hamzar Mt Pringgabaya* ".

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses descriptive qualitative methods. Descriptive method is uses to describe, explain, and analysis the phenomenon which occurs behind the data. Sutopo states that in descriptive method, the analysis of the data is naturally objective, and factual. It means that the researcher applies a set of procedures which is use for problem solving based on the factual data. This research will be conducted in October and November from 23 October To 7 November, 2024. The location of the research is held at the Hamzar MT Pringgabaya health vocational high school (SMK Kesehatan Hamzar MT Pringgabaya) which has an address on Temanjor Kec. Pringgabaya, East Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara. The source of data is recorder and observation. The recorder will be used to record the data also record the interview, and the observation will be used as a technique to obtain data related to the problem of research. The researcher used three instruments in this research, the first is observation, and the second is the recording process and then the last is the documentation process. There are three activity in

qualitative data analysis. They are data reduction, data display, conclusion drawing / verification (Miles, M. B., & Huberman, 1994).

1. Reducing data

The data reduction process can be done in various ways, such as through selection, summary, or paraphrasing and classifying into larger patterns. In the data analysis process, the researcher used a coding system. The process of labelling and segmenting units of meaning on descriptive or inferential information collected during the research. The aim was not to number the data, but to facilitate the researcher in selecting and classifying data from the data sheets and to assist the researcher in organising and classifying the data.

2. Data Display

After collecting and reducing the data, the researcher analysis the types of speech acts. Display the data in organize and compress information to lead matrices the conclusion. The forms of qualitative data display to include types of, graphs, chart, or network. In this study, the data will presented in the form of table and descriptions.

3. Conclusion Drawing

The last stage in this data analysis technique was concluding. After analysing the data, the researcher concluded the types of speech acts used by the English teacher in informal contexts at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar MT Pringgabaya. Concluding involves pausing to ask questions to consider what the analysed data means, or the discovery of a description of an object that was previously unclear after research becomes more straightforward and more detailed.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The use of speech acts is closely related to the role of the teacher. Apart from being a leader in the classroom, teachers also have various other roles, including as authority figures, mentors, and even friends or parental figures. According to Searle (1976), the speech act intended by the speaker is a directive speech act to encourage the listener to take action in accordance with the speaker's statement. In this study, the teacher communicates his intention to encourage students to perform certain actions.

The discussion is organised to answer the problem formulation of this research. The results of this study include the classification of speech acts used by English teachers at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar MT Pringgabaya including the context of the situation. The researcher tried to explain the types of speech acts used by English teachers at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya and students' responses to the speech acts used by English teachers. Apart from the research objectives, the discussion is presented as follows:

First, this analysis examines the types of speech acts used by English teachers in high school classes, based on Searle's theory. Searle classifies speech acts and one of them includes directive speech acts into five categories: command/command, request, invitation, warning/prohibition, and instruction. suggestions.

Based on the analysis, the researcher identified 146 examples of directive speech acts used by English teachers in high school English classes for grade X. The data were collected from three class sessions, the findings revealed 43 instances of commands/orders, 89 instances of requests, 2 instances of invitations, 4 instances of warnings, and 8 instances of suggestions. The second most frequently used type of directive speech act is command, which indicates that the speaker has full authority over the listener's actions. These roles contribute to creating a positive learning environment, guiding and coaching students, building classroom dynamics, serving as role models, and noticing signs of student difficulties.

Requests are a type of directive speech act that aims to encourage listeners to perform an action in situations where it may not be clear that they will do so, as explained by Searle (1969). By making a request, the speaker assumes that the listener is capable of performing the action. In this study, the researcher identified instances that were classified as requests. The most frequently observed type was requests, as the teacher often used the term "please" during the teaching and learning process. This frequency aligns with insights gained from Ma'ruf, A. (2021), in the thesis on Gordon Ramsay's directive speech acts in the "Hell's Kitchen" TV series. The researcher identified four reasons for the teacher's frequent use of requests: the teacher holds a higher status in terms of knowledge than the students, the teacher aims to be polite by incorporating "please" in requests, the teacher seeks to assist students in completing tasks, and the teacher is familiar with the students' background knowledge.

A suggestion is the process by which one idea leads to another, particularly through the association of concepts. It involves presenting a thought that the listener is encouraged to consider. According to Searle (1969), suggestions are communicated in a factual manner to avoid offending the listener. In the data analysis, the researcher identified 8 instances classified as suggestions. English teachers used suggestions

to provide students with solutions and guidance on the appropriate actions they should take to address challenges.

An invitation is an expression used to request others to come to a place or to ask someone to perform a task. According to the data analysis, there were 2 instances identified as invitations. In the teaching and learning process, English teachers utilized these utterances to guide their students in understanding the material.

Warning is telling someone about possible danger or difficult situation. Warning usually stated by positive imperative which gives treatment of some effects, said by Searle (1969). The researcher found from data analysis there are 4 data that considered as warning. English teachers used warn in teaching and learning proses for students if they make mistakes. For examples, when the teacher know if the students did not read material before they came to class so the teacher warn them if they do like that again they can not come to the teacher class again. The function of warning is to make students more aware and disciplined of teaching and learning process in the classroom.

CONCLUSIONS

In this research, the researcher employed a descriptive qualitative method to examine the types of speech acts according to Austin and Searle's theories, analyzing and identifying the English teacher's utterances in an informal teaching context at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya during the Academic Year 2024/2025. Based on the limitations and problem statements outlined in the study, the researcher concludes the findings as follows:

The types of speech acts used by the English teacher in an informal teaching context at SMK Kesehatan Hamzar Maraqitta'limat Pringgabaya were analyzed, revealing a total of 146 data points. The breakdown of directive speech acts is as follows: commands (43 utterances, 34.95%), requests (89 utterances, 54.06%), suggestions (8 utterances, 6.91%), invitations (2 utterances, 0.81%), and warnings (4 utterances, 3.25%). The most frequently used type of speech act by the English teacher was requests, with 133 utterances, representing 54.06% of the total.

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